

Correlating traditioventions and eco-innovations with martial arts, combat sports, and popular physical activities to create a healthy world

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Abstract

Spitzer advocated the prevention of physical and mental degradation in the youth through the practice of martial arts and combat sports (MACS). Unlike sports, MACS have moral philosophies created by their founders. Although MACS typically do not have sustainability-focused goals, their philosophies and pedagogies of how to use their self-cultivation lessons to build a more sustainable environment. The goal of this study was to determine if MACS practices correlated to traditioventions and eco-innovation beliefs. 157 questionnaires were collected from Polish undergraduate students. Respondents self-reported participation in numerous types of MACS, sports, and diverse other physical activities. 71.3% (n=112) of respondents stated that martial arts could be a traditiovention, 40.1% (n=63) felt that martial arts could also be an eco-innovation, and 21% (n=33) stated that they could be both. *Synthesis:* While this study did not definitely prove a connection between MACS, traditioventions, and eco-innovation, it strongly suggests that a connection exists. Longitudinal studies should be conducted to determine if positive traditioventions and eco-innovations beliefs are formed after MACS practice begins.

Keywords: sustainability, combat systems, self-cultivation, combat sports, sport pedagogy, martial arts, traditioventions

Introduction

Corporations and politics have propagated uncontrolled civilizational goals that, despite their best intentions, have wrought many more detriments than merits. These efforts are often unambiguous contradictions to their parallel sustainable development efforts. Furthermore, during the COVID-19 epidemic, various governments exacerbated problems related to sustainability goals by ignoring medical and biological data and limiting the movement of their peoples, thereby denying them access to sunlight and the natural immune-resistant synthesis of vitamin D, which are imperative to preventing biological and mental degradation in the youth (Cynarski 2017; Pawelec 2020). Furthermore, this increased the global youth's use and access to electronic media, smartphones, computers, and sometimes deceptive television and thereby prevented them from participating in safe and healthy outdoor activities. Manfred Spitzer – a German scientist, psychiatrist, and neurologist–predicted these types of problems many earlier (Spitzer 2013; 2021), and yet no one heeded his warnings.

One method of preventing physical and mental degradation in the youth is practicing one or more types of martial arts and combat sports (MACS) (Spitzer 2013; 2021) during one's leisure time. For the purposes of this paper, we have adopted the definition for martial arts as the following: “A *martial art* is a system of self-defense with the ultimate goal of self-cultivation” (Johnson et al., 2015, p. 68). Many martial arts' pedagogies, and especially those of Chinese, Japanese, and Korean origin, advocate peace and contributing to social betterment as final learning objectives (Johnson et al., 2015; Johnson 2017; Johnson 2018). In these activities, the participants cultivate themselves however they see fit through the physical skills and wisdom they acquire during practice. *Combat sports* are alternatively “the competitive side of martial arts” where participants gain wisdom and self-improvement through preparation for and participation in competition (Johnson et al., 2015, p. 69).

One of the most underrated aspects of martial arts practice—as well as a key difference between their practice and that of combat sports – is that being ‘the best’ or great in a martial art is unimportant. Martial arts studies are journeys of self-discovery. Thus, martial arts practice is a method of self-cultivation where a practitioner learns about themselves and realizes how to become a better version of themselves. Indeed, these are the so-called martial arts' ultimate objectives for their martial arts practice (Johnson 2017). Trophies, titles, ranks, and other accolades as well as becoming killing machines, invincible warriors, or champions can be goals practitioners can aim for, but they are ultimately just steps along a path to becoming a better human being. The aim of martial arts practice is thus to learn about yourself and, as above, to become a better person through the physical practice of one's chosen martial art. Participation in combat sports activities and competition can provide similar physical, mental, and emotional benefits (Croom 2014; Dziwenka 2014; Woodward 2009), but all too

often combat sports promote “more vices than virtues” (Bäck 2009, p. 217). Here then is revealed a subtle yet important difference in pedagogical strategies.

Like many health experts today, Spitzer (2013; 2021) advocated replacing a sedentary lifestyle in front of a computer with some form of physical activity. Studies have indicated that MACS are effective means of physical education that provide additional social and emotional benefits (Kim et al., 2015; Biernat et al., 2018; Ying 2019; Bielec et al., 2021). While detriments of these practices include physical dangers inherent with any physical activity and actually have a higher concussion rate than other contact sports such as basketball, American football, ice hockey, and soccer (Lystad et al., 2017), the majority of evidence indicates MACS partitioners’ lives can be improved physically, mentally, and emotionally (Kim et al., 2020).

The philosophy of economy and society based on wisdom was first introduced in Poland by Kukliński (2011) who backed the definition of wisdom of being the integration of knowledge, imagination, experience, and awareness of the canons of good and evil. In an economy based on wisdom, imagination should be a vehicle for the development of processes based on vision and strategic thinking. Additionally, introducing ethical practices into developing 21st century economies and societies is of fundamental importance. We see a clear lack of ethics and an inability to apply wisdom learned from misdeeds in the actions of many of today’s governments when evaluating their responses to environmental concerns. The role of wisdom should be clearly visible in matters of sustainability, since the human race as a whole has the ability to communicate their experiences and wisdom learned from their triumphs and errors (Roos 2017). Other authors have also touched upon this issue (Liao et al., 2016; Yang 2013; Patten 2016; Roos 2017).

One emerging area of sustainability research centers on traditioventions, and some correlations with martial arts studies can be made. Within sustainability literature, traditioventions are defined as: “practices and techniques deriving from historical or past traditional knowledge or re-invented practices and techniques, however, linked to traditional knowledge, showing, thanks also to the support of science and research, a capability to operate as innovation, despite their apparently obsolete and out-of-date features, in production and management” (Cannarella et al., 2011, p. 691).

As evident from the global popularity mixed martial arts (MMA) training and military hand-to-hand training programs taught to civilians, the older martial arts like Taekwondo, Karate, and Kung Fu are now no longer considered the ultimate in self-defense. Many MACS can be considered as outdated or limited combat systems, because more effective means of training for combat have been devised. For the purposes of this paper, we are defining *combat systems* as “organized systems of self-defense or fighting that may or may not incorporate weapons, which possess the ultimate objective of protecting

one's country, property, or self" (Johnson et al., 2015, p. 67). Consequently, most popular martial arts and their combat sports offshoots practiced today can be understood as traditioventions, since they are not utilized in actual preparation for combat by the world's modern militaries.

Purpose of the study

The aim of our study was to determine if MACS practice may influence practitioners' attitudes toward traditioventions and eco-innovations. The correlating factor between MACS and traditioventions and eco-innovations is the application of wisdom gained from experience. Therefore, this study utilized three theoretical lenses: a traditiovention lens, Cynarski's General Theory of Fighting Arts (Cynarski 2017), and Johnson and Ha's (2015) pedagogical lens for combat systems, martial arts, and combat sports. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first such study that intended to show a practical application of wisdom gained from MACS from a traditiovention lens. It was hoped that this study would thereby support the theory that MACS practices provide something more than mere pugilistic aggression (Johnson 2018).

Materials and Methods

Procedure

The present quantitative study utilized a diagnostic survey by distributing a questionnaire to university undergraduate students in Rzeszów, Poland. A questionnaire was specially developed and used as the tool. Data was collected through the questionnaire that consisted of fourteen questions: multiple choice questions (n=6), 7 Yes/No questions (n=7), and a short answer question (n=1). The questions determined respondents' preferred use of leisure time (tourism, martial arts, or other); the number of hours they engaged in their indicated leisure time activity; the type of martial art practiced; their martial art rank; and what martial arts activities they participate in (e.g., training seminars, competitions, academic conferences, training camps, etc.). Respondents were allowed to indicate more than one choice when indicating their preferred type of recreational activity in order to elucidate the roll physical activity has on traditiovention and eco-innovation as well as to provide a larger sample population.

YES/NO questions also determined if respondents' felt modern solutions in MACS could be considered eco-innovations and if MACS met the definition of traditiovention (i.e., traditional solutions in a new formula). Respondents additionally answered a multiple-choice question that determined their attitude towards the environment, ecology, and sustainable development; the provided opinions to this

question were: “unequivocally pro-ecological,” “moderately pro-ecological,” “moderately indifferent to ecological concerns,” and “indifferent to ecological concerns.”

The final question on the questionnaire was a short answer question that requested respondents to describe the actions they take to maintain their overall physical health. Succeeding the data collection portion of the questionnaire were 8 demographic questions that collected respondents’ gender, year of birth, university attended, academic discipline studied, whether that discipline was their first field of study (i.e., if they were double majors or working on a second degree), years studied, nationalities, and university location. This data was used to ensure a broad sample population had been selected.

Statistical analysis

Data were compiled with the use of simple statistical analysis methods: standard deviation and percentage indicators. Pearson’s correlation analysis was used to evaluate the number of hours of time spent on organized training per week and the number of hours outside of organized training allocated to the development of sports skills. The independent variables were the understanding of the management process, the treatment of trainings, the purpose of trainings, and participants’ genders.

Participants

The two Polish authors received consent from their universities and a third university in Wroclaw, Poland to conduct this survey. Selection criteria was set at Polish undergraduate university students. Due to the mandated social distancing constraints put into place due to the COVID-19 pandemic at the researchers’ universities, questionnaires were emailed to students in the authors’ undergraduate courses in accordance with university guidelines. A total of 200 questionnaires were emailed randomly to students enrolled in the researchers’ undergraduate courses. All returned questionnaires that were completed incorrectly (n=43) were rejected. One of the Polish authors collected 127 properly completed questionnaires, and the other collected 30 properly completed questions. A total of 157 questionnaires were therefore used to determine the results of this study.

Ethical principles

Approval of the Idokan Poland Association ethics review committee, including research methods, was conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki 2008.

Results

Out of the 157 questionnaires (male=70; female=87) received, 148 respondents self-reported having practiced some form of MACS. The percentage of respondents practicing MACS and the type of MACS they practice are shown in Figure 1. Respondents could indicate more than one activity. Karate (n=38) and Jujutsu (n=31) were the most commonly practiced martial arts among this study’s

respondents. “Other” was the third most indicated category (participants in this group did not write in a specific MACS). Kickboxing (n=21) was the fourth most popular activity reported, and this was followed by boxing (n=10) and mixed martial arts (MMA) (n=8). Although not a martial art, five respondents wrote in football (soccer) as another activity; these answers were not rejected because the respondents also indicated a MACS in their responses. Surprisingly, due to its global popularity (Yoon, 2021), only six respondents claimed to practice Taekwondo (n=3) or Kung Fu (n=3). Some MACS only had one respondent indicate they practiced them: Capoeira, Aiki-jujutsu, Krav Maga (an Israeli martial art), Systema (a Russian martial art), western fencing, and Brazilian Jujutsu.

Figure 1. Respondents’ self-reported type of MACS practiced and the percentages of those who practice them

MACS: martial arts/combat sports; MMA: mixed martial arts

Source: own research.

Many styles of each type of MACS exist. Typically, MACS curriculums do not include tradition or eco-innovation components, and none of the reported MACS have traditions; consequently, the differences between the MACS and their various offshoots would not affect the results of this study. Rather than delineate the meticulous numerous differences in the MACS styles the respondents reported, all types of a particular martial art were grouped into one category for the purposes of this study. Consequently, Idokan Karate, Shotokan Karate, Gojuryu Karate, and all other styles of Karate were collated under the “Karate” category, and the same was performed for all other MACS listed in Figure 1.

Of the 157 respondents, 132 individuals self-reported participating in sporting and physical activities in addition to MACS. The most preferred method of physical activity among the respondents

were team sports such as football (soccer) and volleyball (n=28). The second most popular forms of physical exercise were going to a fitness center (n=22), running (n=22), and cycling (n=22). Hiking (n=7), inline skating (n=7), and other forms of physical activity (n=7) were third most popular, and home training (n=4) and swimming (n=4) were the least popular among respondents. The percentage of respondents practicing a sport or engaging in types of physical activities other than MACS as well as what type of activity they engage in are shown in Figure 2.

Source: own research.

Respondents also self-reported the approximate number of hours they participate in martial arts, combat sports, or other athletic practices per week (Table 1). All respondents reported training between 1 and 4 hours a week, indicating they participate in these activities only during their leisure time and in a limited fashion. The mean for the number of hours spent training was 2.5, and the standard deviation was 1.04 (Table 1).

Table 1. Self-reported number of hours that respondents train per week; number of respondents = 157	
	Hours per week of training
Minimum	1
Maximum	4
Mean	2.5
SD	1.04
SD: standard deviation	

Source: own research.

Cynarski, Kuśnierz, and Witkowski (2012) found “attitudes towards martial arts depend ([i.e., they are] directly proportional) on the knowledge of respondents” and that “the evaluation of martial arts value depends on the respondents’ level of knowledge ([of] martial arts).” Accordingly, respondents’ knowledge of MACS needed to be taken into account to determine the amount of wisdom they amassed from their MACS practice. A metric was therefore needed to ascertain this, despite the fact that wisdom is incalculable. Luckily, martial arts typically have rank systems to indicate a practitioner’s level of knowledge and ability in that art, unlike sports and even many combat sports. The longer a person practices a martial art, the more likely their practice will influence the logic and the thinking strategies they employ in their daily lives (Johnson 2017). This is because the longer a person is exposed to an activity and philosophy, even a philosophy of movement, the more likely they will adopt, adapt, and incorporate the lessons learned from that activity into other areas of their lives. Consequently, Table 2 lists the respondents’ self-reported martial arts ranks and the approximate time the respondent has practiced their preferred martial art.

Respondents did not report how long they have practiced their MACS, and only a few respondents (n=11) provided their rank (Table 1). Consequently, this data only provides a glimpse into how rank may factor into respondents’ understanding of MACS as a tradition or innovation. This data was not incorporated into the findings of this study but is presented here nonetheless as respondents’ MACS demographic data.

Martial arts rank	Number of respondents who indicated their MACS ranks (n=11)	Approximate time practiced (years)
White belt	1	0.1
Yellow stripe	1	0.2
Orange belt	1	0.3
4 <i>kyu</i>	1	0.6
Green belt	1	0.6
9.3 <i>kyu</i>	1	1
1 <i>dan</i>	3	4-5
2 <i>dan</i>	1	5-6
4 <i>dan</i>	1	10
<i>Kyu</i> : Japanese for color belt; <i>dan</i> : Japanese and Korean for black belt		

Source: own research.

The approximate times listed in Table 2 are based on the idea that practitioners will advance in rank once every 2-3 months and will earn a 1 *dan* (first degree black belt) within 4 years of continuous martial arts practice. Martial arts rank systems typically begin with a white belt and progress into darker colors until the black belt levels (i.e., the *dan* ranks) are reached. A new *dan* rank is typically awarded after a student has practiced continually for the same number of years as their current rank. Hence, a first *dan* martial arts practitioner may be eligible for second *dan* after one year of practice, a 2 *dan* practitioner may be eligible for third *dan* after two years of practice, and so on. While some combat sports such as western fencing, Kickboxing, and MMA may have a rank system, this study did not consider those activities as martial arts in accordance with Johnson and Ha (2015), who would have defined them as combat sports due to those activities overwhelming focus on competition. Thus, respondents only provided their ranks in martial arts such as Karate, Taekwondo, Aiki-jujutsu, Kung Fu, and Brazilian Jujutsu practitioners, which can possess competitive components but that do not require competition to learn and progress in ability and wisdom.

Respondents were asked to indicate if their martial arts practice was a method of spending their leisure time (n=105) or a priority for them (n=65) (Figure 3). This question was intended to further determine the level of importance the practice was to the respondent as well as indicate their willingness to accept, adopt, adopt, and incorporate martial art lessons into their daily lives. Figure 4 shows what the respondents' reported. Some respondents indicated that martial arts practice was both a means of leisure time and a priority for them, which explains the disparity in percentages. As a person can consider how they spend their leisure time a priority, the questionnaires that reported that martial arts were a means of spending leisure time as well as a priority were accepted and incorporated into the findings of this study.

Figure 3. Percentages of respondents who indicated MACS is a means of spending leisure time or a priority. Some respondents indicated that it was both.

MACS: martial arts/combat sports

Source: own research.

All three authors belong to various international martial arts organizations; to ensure a diverse study population, respondents were thus asked to indicate their martial arts and sports organizational memberships. Respondents could write in the names of their affiliation's names. Some of the respondent belonged to Polish national professional basketball and football (soccer) teams and are therefore public figures. Accordingly, these team names are reported in Figure 4 as "Polish Basketball Team" or "Polish Football (Soccer) Team" to protect the respondents' anonymity. Other respondents indicated allegiance to a private, local physical fitness clubs or privately-owned sporting academy. The names of these businesses were changed to "Polish Football (Soccer) Academy 1," "Polish Football (Soccer) Academy 2," "Local Polish Fitness Club," and "Polish Acrobatics Club" (Figure 4).

Not every respondent declared an affiliation, so Figure 4 only indicates those that did so. "Polish Basketball Team" (n=4) and "Polish Football (Soccer) Team" (n=4) had the greatest number of associations. The Idokan Poland Association (Sieber et al., 2013) had the second number of affiliations (n=3). All other organizations listed in Figure 4 had only one respondent claim affiliation to it.

Figure 4. Respondents' Martial arts and sport organizations. Not all respondents indicated membership to an organization. Some names of organizations and clubs were changed to protect respondents' anonymity.

BMC = The British Mountaineering Council; IPA = Idokan Poland Association

Source: own research.

Respondents were asked about their martial arts training goals. Two options were provided: respondents could indicate if they were motivated by a desire to improve their physical and mental capabilities or to perform at world-class level. 88.2% (n=105) of the respondents indicated they

participate in MACS to improve their physical and mental, and 11.8% (n=14) stated they practice MACS to achieve a world-class level (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Respondents' martial arts training goals. Only two options were available. Amounts presented in percentages.

Source: own research.

As the primary objective of the current study was to elucidate respondents' concern for and association with MACS to eco-innovation, the questionnaire also asked respondents if MACS could be considered a tradition, eco-innovation, or both. A majority (71.3%; n=112) of respondents stated that martial arts could be a tradition. Somewhat surprisingly, 40.1% (n=63) of the respondents felt that martial arts could also be an eco-innovation, while 21% (n=33) stated that they could be both (Figure

6) according to the above-provided definitions.

Figure 6. Percentage of respondents who believe martial arts are a tradition, eco-innovation, or both.

Source: own research.

Respondents self-reported their attitude towards the environment, ecology, and sustainable development in order to determine any personal bias in their answers to our questionnaire. They were provided four options: unequivocally pro-ecological, moderately pro-ecological, moderately indifferent to ecological concerns, and indifferent to ecological concerns. As shown in Figure 7, 31 respondents

(19.7%) of the respondents identified as unequivocally pro-ecological, 112 (71.2%) reported themselves as moderately pro-ecological, 12 individuals (7.6%) reported being moderately indifferent to ecological concerns, and only 2 respondents (1.3%) reported being indifferent to ecological concerns (Figure 7).

Figure 7. Percentages of respondents who self-reported their unequivocally pro-ecological, moderately pro-ecological, moderately indifferent to ecological concerns, and indifferent to ecological concerns biases.

Source: own research.

To further eliminate potential bias, we bifurcated respondents' answers to the unequivocally pro-ecological, moderately pro-ecological, moderately indifferent to ecological concerns, and indifferent to ecological concerns question according to gender (Figure 8). While the two genders self-reported similar biases percentages, women were slightly higher in being unequivocally and moderately pro-ecological. More specifically, 20.7% (n=18) of the women and 18.6% (n=13) of the men reported being unequivocally pro-ecological; 72.4% (n=63) of the women and 70% (n=13) of the men reported being moderately pro-ecological; 6.9% (n=6) of the women and 8.6% (n=13) of the men reported being moderately indifferent to ecological concerns; and 0.0% (n=0) of the women and 2.9% of the men reported being completely indifferent to ecological concerns (Figure 8).

Figure 8. Percentages of respondents who self-reported their unequivocally pro-ecological, moderately pro-ecological, moderately indifferent to ecological concerns, and indifferent to ecological concerns biases according to gender.

Source: own research.

Although differing in size and nature, a healthy, biologically efficient organism is the required for effective sports practice as well as ecology. The types of health prophylaxis activities self-reported by the respondents correlate their preferred methods of maintaining their physical to mental health and ecology. Respondents were required to write in their preferred methods of health prophylaxis. As Figure 9 shows, the majority of respondents followed a proper diet (30.8%; n=100). Respondents also self-reported having an active lifestyle (28.9%; n=94), exercising (16.3%; n=53), following a good sleep health program (7.1%; n=23), learning about healthy living (5.5%; n=18), taking supplements and being vaccinated (3.7%; n=12), avoiding stimulants (3.1%; n=10), avoiding stress (1.5%; n=5), maintaining personal hygiene (1.2%; n=4), participating in tourist activities (1.2%; n=4), and engaging in other health prophylaxis means (0.6%; n=2) (Figure 9).

Figure 9. Types of health prophylaxis activities self-reported by the respondents.

Source: own research.

Discussion

The present study examined the intersection of traditiovation and MACS studies to ascertain if the wisdom gained MACS and other physical activities have influence over practitioners' attitudes toward traditioventions and eco-innovations. A questionnaire was employed to survey Polish undergraduate students, and 157 independent responses were received. The data from these responses indicate that, for at least the current study population, MACS practice and other physical activities such as sports and active lifestyles may influence individual's attitudes regarding traditioventions and eco-innovations. Adequate diet was determined to be the most important factor in maintaining good health. Among the preferred martial arts, most respondents practiced kickboxing and boxing, but in total, they practiced numerous forms MACS including various types of Karate and Jujitsu.

At first glance, it may seem that MACS would have little correlation with the agricultural concerns of traditioventions and eco-innovations. However, many founders of MACS systems – in particular those originating in China, Korea, and Japan – espoused the benefits of agriculture (Stevens 1986; Funakoshi 1981), which mostly have Buddhist influences (Mann 2012). This suggests a novel research area for both environmental and martial arts studies. What is meant by martial arts traditioventions? There can be many interpretations and there are, but it is most simply presented in one of the first publications on this issue, the authors of which interpret this concept. Cannarella and Piccioni (2011) support this new direction of research by stating that traditioventions are based on long-established cultural norms, traditions, and ancient techniques for development.

Most significant to this study was that 71.3% (n=112) of respondents stated that MACS could be considered traditioventions, 40.1% (n=63) of respondents felt that MACS could be an eco-innovation, and 21% of respondents (n=33) stated that MACS could be both (Figure 6). This finding indicates that the vast majority of respondents could correlate MACS to the above definition of traditiovention and eco-innovation. This suggestion was somewhat mitigated by the fact that 19.7% of respondents (n=31) self-identified themselves as unequivocally pro-ecological, and that 71.2% (n=112) 7.6% (n=12) self-reporting being moderately pro-ecological and moderately indifferent to ecological concerns, respectively. With only 2 respondents (1.3%) reported being indifferent to ecological concerns, it seems that most of the study population may have possessed pro traditiovention and eco-innovative beliefs (Figure 7). The data here may be inconclusive in helping to determine a correlation between MACS practice and a favorable attitude toward traditioventions and eco-innovations. Nevertheless, the high percentage of respondents who practiced MACS and engaged in other physical activities and who are also positively inclined toward traditiovention and eco-innovative beliefs indicates the strong possibility of correlation between the two groups.

The majority (n=148) of the study population, Polish undergraduate university students, indicated that they had practiced some form of MACS (Figure 1). Respondents self-reported having studied numerous forms of MACS that enjoy worldwide popularity, including MMA, Karate, Kung Fu, Taekwondo, and Jujitsu, but less popular MACS were also represented in the study population. These included Iaido, Capoeira, Aiki-jujutsu, Systema, and Krav Maga. These results indicate that MACS practice is varied and widespread within the respondents, thus providing a greater opportunity for that practice to influence their attitudes toward traditioventions and eco-innovations.

A large percentage of respondents also self-reported participating in other forms of physical activity, including team sports such as volleyball and football (soccer); nevertheless, most respondents indicated a preference for individual, non-organized physical activities such as hiking, inline skating, running, and personal training at fitness centers. The data showed the study population held physical activities as important to their overall lifestyle (Figure 9), which was supported by their associations with various sport, physical activity, and MACS organizations (Figure 4). However, this was tempered somewhat by the fact that their mean number of hours of physical activity per week was only 2.5 hours (Table 1). Nonetheless, this data indicates physical activities outside of MACS practice may have influenced respondents' attitudes toward traditioventions and eco-innovations.

A potential for bias was considered due to the two Polish authors' affiliation with large, international MACS organizations and the use of some students at their universities for this study. However, only 29.2% of the study population held affiliation to a MACS organization (e.g., the Polish Boxing Association, Bushi-do Martial Arts and Self-Defense Exhibition, Polish Karate Association, and the Idokan Poland Association) (Figure 4). Thus, bias was avoided by randomly emailing the questionnaire to the three universities.

Conclusions

The present study revealed Polish undergraduate students actively spend their leisure time practicing various types of physical activities, including MACS. Respondents declared their appropriate pro-health and pro-ecological attitudes. The vast majority of respondents also indicated interests in traditioventions and eco-innovations, which suggests that MACS practice could influence students' traditioventions and eco-innovations beliefs. Many respondents also reported other non-MACS physical activity interests ranging from playing organized Western sports to working out at privately-owned gymnasiums.

While the current research, which should be considered a pilot study, did not reveal a definite correlation between traditioventions and eco-innovations and MACS practice, there is sufficient

evidence to suggest that a correlation between them does exist. Thus, future research is warranted, including into how MACS practice could enhance or traditioventions and eco-innovations beliefs. Furthermore, many MASC promote peace and contributing to social betterment as final learning objectives (Johnson et al., 2015; Johnson, 2017, 2018). Eco-innovations could be considered means to these learning objectives and thus enhance practitioners' MACS practice. Researchers should also investigate how a traditiovention and eco-innovation lens could help guide MACS students toward their practice goals.

This study has several limitations including a study population that was limited to Polish university students who reported a wide range of physical activities. These two factors prevent a definitive correlation between MACS practice and traditioventions and eco-innovations. However, many respondents reported studying MACS whose founders followed eco-friendly philosophies. While none of the MACS reported in this research espouse an overt traditiovention or eco-innovation philosophy that could influence respondents, the large majority of respondents' inclination toward them indicates a correlation between MACS and traditioventions and eco-innovations.

Furthermore, one factor not incorporated into this study's conclusions is the amount of time respondents spent practicing MACS. It is obvious that the longer one is willingly exposed to a certain philosophy, the more likely they will follow it. Thus, future studies should be longitudinal in nature, and researchers should ascertain on MACS practitioners' traditiovention or eco-innovation beliefs prior to participating in MACS.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest in the composition of this research.

Author Contributions

Wojciech J. Cynarski assisted in the study design, data collection, statistical analysis, data interpretation, and literature review. John A. Johnson performed the manuscript preparation and assisted in the statistical analysis, data interpretation, and literature review. Leszek Woźniak assisted in the study design, data collection, statistical analysis, data interpretation, and literature review. Przemysław Pawelec performed the manuscript preparation.

Data Availability Statement

Data accrued for this study shall be stored within the Department of Entrepreneurship, Management and Ecoinnovations at Rzeszow University of Technology, which is located in Rzeszow, Poland.

References

1. Bäck A. The way to virtue in sport. *Journal of the Philosophy of Sport*. 2009; 36(2): 217-237. doi: 10.1080/00948705.2009.9714758.
2. Bielec G, Dziadek B, Borysiuk Z, Cynarski WJ. Budo in physical recreation as a form of rapprochement to nature. *Sustainability*. 2021; 13(12): 6951. doi: 10.3390/su13126951.
3. Biernat E, Krzepota J, Sadowska D. Martial arts as a form of undertaking physical activity in leisure time analysis of factors determining participation of Poles. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*. 2018; 15: 1989. doi: 10.3390/ijerph15091989.
4. Cannarella C, Piccioni V. Traditiovations: Creating innovation from the past and antique techniques for rural areas. *Technovation*. 2011; 31(12): 689-699. doi: 10.1016/j.technovation.2011.07.005.
5. Croom AM. Embodying martial arts for mental health: Cultivating psychological well-being with martial arts practice. *Archives of Budo Science of Martial Arts and Extreme Sports*. 2024; 10: 59-70.
6. Cynarski WJ. Towards a General Theory of Fighting Arts. *Physical Activity Review*. 2017; 5: 83-90. doi: 10.16926/par.2017.05.12.
7. Cynarski WJ., Kuśnierz C, Witkowski K. Polish students' knowledge and their attitudes towards martial arts and combat sports. *Ido Movement for Culture Journal of Martial Arts Anthropology*. 2012; 12(3): 5-9.
8. Dziwenka R. Applying a Buddhist paradigm of spiritual practice to contemporary martial art/martial sport study. *Journal of the International Association for Taekwondo Research*. 2014; 1(1): 14-21.
9. Funakoshi G. *Karate-dō: My way of life*. Kodansha International; 1981.
10. Johnson JA. From technique to way: An investigation into Taekwondo's pedagogical process. *Ido Movement for Culture Journal of Martial Arts Anthropology*. 2017; 17(4): 3-13. doi: 10.14589/ido.17.4.2.
11. Johnson JA. Taekwondo and Peace: How a killing art became a soft diplomacy vehicle for peace. *International Journal of the History of Sport*. 2018; 35(15-16): 1637-1662. doi: 10.1080/09523367.2019.1618838
12. Johnson JA, Ha P. Elucidating pedagogical objectives for combat systems, martial arts, and combat sports. *Ido Movement for Culture Journal of Martial Arts Anthropology*. 2015; 15(4): 65-74. doi: 10.14589/ido.15.4.9.

13. Kim DS, Bäck A. Foundations of Taekwondo: History, theory, academics. iACT Publishing; 2020.
14. Kim MK, Lee D, Kim SK, Kim M. Leisure constraints affecting experienced martial arts participants. *Asia Pacific Journal of Tourism Research*. 2015; 20: 1063-1079. doi: 10.1080/10941665.2014.952240.
15. Kukliński A. From an economy based on knowledge to an economy based on wisdom. *Bulletin of PTE*. 2011; 2: 65-68. (in Polish).
16. Liao KH, Chan JKH. What is ecological wisdom and how does it relate to ecological knowledge? *Landscape and Urban Planning*. 2016; 155: 111-113. doi: 10.1016/j.landurbplan.2016.07.006.
17. Lystad RP, Kazemi M, Koh JO., Song JK. Concussion in Taekwondo: A position statement by the International Association for Taekwondo Research. *Acta Taekwondo et Martialis Artium*. 2017; 4(2): 1-4.
18. Mann JK. *When Buddhists attack: The curious relationship between Zen and the martial arts*. Tuttle Publishing; 2012.
19. Patten DT. The role of ecological wisdom in managing for sustainable interdependent urban and natural ecosystems. *Landscape and Urban Planning*. 2016; 155: 3-10. doi: 10.1016/j.landurbplan.2016.01.013.
20. Pawelec P. Martial arts and combat sports. *Towards the General Theory of Fighting Arts: Book review*. *Ido Movement for Culture Journal of Martial Arts Anthropology*. 2020; 20(1): 54-57. doi: 10.14589/ido.20.1.7.
21. Roos J. Practical wisdom: Making and teaching the governance case for sustainability. *Journal of Cleaner Production*. 2017; 140(1): 117-124 [Accessed 22 July 2024]. Available from: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0959652615016091>.
22. Sieber L, Cynarski WJ. A new stage in the history of the Idokan organization. *Ido Movement for Culture Journal of Martial Arts Anthropology*. 2013; 13(3): 59-71. doi: 10.14589/ido.13.3.7.
23. Spitzer M. *How we deprive ourselves and our children of our minds*. Dobra Literatura; 2012. (in Polish).
24. Spitzer M. *The smartphone epidemic*. Dobra Literatura; 2021. (in Polish).
25. Stevens J. *The Shambhala guide to Aikidō*. Shambhala Publications; 1986.
26. Woodward TW. A review of the effects of martial arts practice on health. *Wisconsin Medical Journal*. 2009; 108(1): 40-43.
27. Yang S. Wisdom and good lives: A process perspective. *New Ideas Psychology*. 2013; 31(3): 194-201. doi: 10.1016/j.newideapsych.2013.03.001.

28. Ying L. New ecology: Chinese traditional martial arts culture protection and carry forward game analysis. *Ekoloji*. 2019; 28(107): 2773-2778.

Yoon JY. World Taekwondo to commemorate decades-long journey toward world peace. *The Korea Times*; 2021 Nov [Accessed 22 July 2024]. Available from: https://www.koreatimes.co.kr/www/sports/2021/11/600_318950.html.